

PERCEPTIONS OF PSDB IMPLEMENTATION AND OPERATIONALIZATION: AN ANALYSIS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF ACCOUNTING PROFESSIONALS AT IRATI – PR

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Adriana Dvulathca

Accountant from the State University of the Midwest (UNICENTRO), specialist in corporate taxation and controllership. Email: adriana_duvi@hotmail.com

Telma Regina Stroparo

PhD student at PPGG-UEPG, Master in Regional Development, works as a Professor at the State University of the Midwest (UNICENTRO). E-mail: telma@unicentro.br

Abstract: The dynamics with which technological changes happen are not always accompanied by accountants, since the routine inside an office sometimes does not allow time for such updates. However, tax technology is more complex and requires the accounting professional to have other types of knowledge, such as computerized systems and ancillary obligations with respect to taxes and other accounting requirements. The accountant needs to be up to date and attentive to every change that has taken place and is able to undergo these changes, since the market is more demanding. These changes are unified in projects, for example, the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB), which came to reduce deviations, prevent the issue of fraud or omission of pertinent data in this sense, the technological knowledge of the accountant needs to be updated, so that next to the taxpayer at the time of the implementation of PSDB, can give the necessary support for the doubts and problems that may occur. In view of the above, the research aims to verify perceptions of the implementation of PSDB according to the accounting professionals of Irati-PR. It is justified to verify the process of implementation of the same and, according to the operationalization, to point out the obstacles faced by accounting professionals when the subject is a Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System. **Keywords:** Accounting. Information Technology. Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB).

INTRODUCTION

In Brazil, the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB) was instituted by Decree No. 6,022 of January 22, 2007 and is considered an integral system of the Growth Acceleration Program (PAC) 2007-2010, in terms of measures intended for the improvement and exemption of the tax system (SILVA et al, 2018; SABIN; STROPARO, 2015).

The institution of PSDB has immediate effects on the daily life of the accounting profession, which is faced with a more complex tax technology and requires professionals to have other types of knowledge, such as information technology and ancillary obligations regarding taxes and other accounting requirements. The "digital age" has led to several adaptations in the routine and renewal of knowledge in the accounting field. Technological innovation and the need for updating by professionals are discussed. (KSCHEVY; STROPARO, 2022; PORDEUS; STROPARO, 2021; PRZYBYCZEWSKI; STROPARO, 2021; RAMOS; STROPARO; CORDEIRO, 2021; SANTIN; STROPARO, 2022) .

The "digital age" has led to several adaptations in the routine and renewal of knowledge in the accounting field. According to Nunes (2004), information technology is an increasingly strategic and crucial resource for competitive advantage and, therefore, for the survival of the company.

However, to accomplish these digital knowledge updates, time is a key element. How long can it take for the professional to seek qualification and maintain it to assume greater commitments with their clients? Sometimes this time is one that the professional does not have.

Another point that the accountant needs to be aware of is with regard to tax, social security and corporate legislation. Blau et. al. (2013) comments that, given this, accounting offices act as mediation instruments in the taxpayer x tax relationship, which increasingly leads them to provide accounting information more promptly, since it is observed that any inaccurate data transmitted can mean a notification on my way. In addition, the accountant assumes joint and several liability in the civil and criminal spheres for any inconsistencies in the information passed on to the tax authorities.

In this sense, art. 1,177, sole paragraph, of Law nº 10,406 (Brazil, 2002), provides that, in the performance of their duties, the accountant is jointly and severally liable with the company for willful acts committed before third parties.

All these details that the accounting professional needs to be aware of, that is, technological changes; knowledge updates; business competitiveness; time optimization; Tax tax knowledge and joint responsibility are unified in a project called the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB), which came to reduce deviations, prevent the issuance of fraud or omission of relevant data. (KSCHEVY; STROPARO, 2022; PORDEUS; STROPARO, 2021; PRZYBYCZEWSKI; STROPARO, 2021).

In the information generated for PSDB, the responsibility is even greater, as the level of detail within a digital file formatted for sending to the Federal or State Revenue Service is very

broad and specific. Information ranging from product registrations to details of invoice observations is included.

In this sense, the technological knowledge of the accountant needs to be up to date, so that, alongside the taxpayer at the time of implementation and operationalization of the PSDB, it can provide the necessary support for the doubts and problems that may occur. Given the above, the research aims to verify perceptions of the implementation of PSDB according to accounting professionals in Irati-PR. It is justified by verifying its implementation process and, according to its operationalization, pointing out the obstacles faced by accounting professionals when it comes to the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System.

SEARCH PROBLEM

According to Fabretti, et. al. (2013), tax legislation has often created new ancillary obligations for providing information to the tax authorities. In addition, non-compliance with these obligations entails high fines for the entrepreneur and the accountant. These tax obligations are declarations that are transmitted to the competent government, be it federal, state or municipal. With the advent of technology, advisory obligations have become digital, making companies and accountants adapt to the format.

The government's interest is to standardize the way in which information is delivered, control and optimization of data provided by accounting, which facilitates and streamlines the crossing of data. It also brings a series of benefits, such as reducing the issue of paper documents, standardizing information between tax authorities, combating fraud in information and also commercial secrecy in the information presented.

Faced with the complexity of the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB), the accountant's responsibilities and the search for updating for the best performance of the profession, the problem question of the work is: What are the perceptions of the implementation and operation of the PSDB for the accounting professionals of Irati / PR?

The main purpose of the study is to describe the perceptions of the PSDB implementation and operationalization process by accounting professionals in Irati-PR. The study of the subject is relevant, not only for companies directly or indirectly involved with PSDB, but also for accounting students, professionals in the area and fields linked to the management process in general. It is justified by bringing a subject that has an impact on the way accounting operations are carried out and also influences the level of professionalism of the accountant because it needs constant updating. In order to better understand the perceptions of accounting professionals about the implementation and operation of PSDB, taking into

account the profession and the obstacles caused by this new way of presenting information to the tax authorities, this study was limited to professionals in the accounting area, who work with member accountants of the Association of Accountants of Irati – PR.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Accounting and Information Technology

Accounting is in constant technological evolution. It is currently undergoing changes, in which to ensure modernization, parameterization of information is essential, making it more accurate and more relevant (KSCHEVY; STROPARO, 2022; KOHUT; STROPARO, 2022; SABIN; STROPARO, 2015).

This technological growth in accounting has made it more agile and practical, benefiting companies. There have been changes in the way these companies are structured, operate, market and interrelate (KSCHEVY; STROPARO, 2022; KOHUT; STROPARO, 2022; SABIN; STROPARO, 2015)

Oliveira (2003) states that the benefits of computerized accounting are increased productivity, improved quality of services, more encouragement for professionals in the area, ease of reading reports in advance, meeting the requirements of bodies regarding compliance with deadlines, ease of access to company information, more information security, less physical space in work environments.

Technology has affected the market in general and when it comes to the national tax system, professionals in the accounting area must be prepared to apply inspection, when it comes to fraud and tax evasion practiced by companies causing losses to the tax authorities (KSCHEVY; STROPARO, 2022; KOHUT; STROPARO, 2022; SABIN; STROPARO, 2015)

Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB)

The Public System of Digital Bookkeeping – PSDB, refers to a technological solution that standardizes the digital files of accounting and tax bookkeeping of the management systems used by companies within a specific and standardized layout.

Generally speaking, PSDB can be identified as a software, made available by the Federal Revenue Service of Brazil, for companies to allocate information of an accounting and tax nature and also social security information, as well as tax, commercial and accounting books generated from their bookkeeping, in addition to financial statements formatted by accounting professionals.

PSDB is part of the Tax and Customs Administration Modernization Project (PMATA) and the Federal Government's Growth Acceleration Program 18 (PAC 2007-2010). The latter institutes PSDB through Decree No. 6022 of January 22, 2007.

The PSDB project has the following main objectives: to promote the integration of tax authorities, rationalize and standardize ancillary obligations for taxpayers and speed up the identification of tax offenses. (FEDERAL REVENUE OF BRAZIL, 2014).

METHODOLOGY

In the present work, the research model regarding the objectives is survey. The method used consists of using the instrument - a practical questionnaire applied to a sample of professionals linked to accounting offices in Irati-PR, divided into 5 blocks and composed of 22 questions related to the perception of professionals in relation to PSDB.

As for the approach to the problem, it can be characterized as qualitative and quantitative. At the end of the professionals' responses, the data will be tabulated in the form of spreadsheets and graphs to identify the perception of accounting professionals. The population where the research is inserted are the professionals who work in the accounting offices that are members of the association of accountants in the city of Irati-PR. The questionnaire was made available electronically in the form of a link sent by email to the previously selected offices. Respondents declare awareness and agreement with the Free and Informed Consent Form (TCLE).

Research Data

To respond to the objectives, a questionnaire was applied aimed at the perception of professionals regarding the implementation of PSDB. The aim was to detect the professionals' point of view on the subject. The questionnaire was separated into 5 (five) blocks: General Information; Accounting professional analysis; Deployment process; Post-Implementation Routines; PSDB perceptions.

Block 1 seeks to identify the professional with his basic data, such as gender, age and technical training. Block 2 aimed to identify the companies that professionals are responsible for, as well as the number, the sector where they work and in which PSDB subproject companies are obliged to provide information to the tax authorities. Block 3, in turn, concerns the actual implementation of PSDB in companies, how it happened and what was the professional's influence on it. As for Block 4, questions were asked about the routine activities of a company that has the obligation to deliver information to PSDB, how this occurs and how the accounting

professional works. Finally, in Block 5, professionals reported their perceptions regarding the researched topic.

Analyzing the data, it is highlighted that half of the professionals questioned are aged up to 25 years old, and still 28% are between 26 to 35 years old and the others over 36 years old, with the percentage of men and women being identical, being 50% each. In the figure below, we can see age groups and gender.

Figure 1 Age Groups and Gender

Source: The authors

It is observable in Figure 1 the research data regarding the age and gender of the respondents. There is equality between males and females and most are up to 25 years old.

The time of experience in the accounting area and the type of professional were also analyzed. It was found that half of the sample is working in the accounting area for a period of up to 5 years, and a portion that corresponds to 28% is between 6 and 10 years. Those who have been working for more than 11 years represent 22%. Professional accountants who work in accounting offices add up to 67% and internal accountants who work in a single private company are 17%. Other accounting areas also represent 17%. Half of the sample has been working in the field for up to 5 years and of these 67% are already trained accountants who are working with several companies in an office. This scenario can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2 Period of performance and Function

Source: The authors

Starting with an approach on the implementation of PSDB, it was questioned which PSDB project has the greatest impact on the profession, regarding the complexity of configuration and data validation. More than one response was obtained from each professional, and with 38% of the percentage, it was reported that the EFD ICMS/IPI and/or Contributions, that is, the PSDB's that are delivered monthly, one by the 12th of each month and the other up to the 10th of the month following the accrual are those that cause the most impact, as their particularities are complex. Electronic invoice designs in all their models ranked third in impact for the profession, with a percentage of 24%.

Accordingly, the ECD and ECF projects represented 10% and 29% respectively, also having a considerable level of impact, since these projects are the union of the others mentioned in the question, with delivery once in each calendar year. In parallel, it was also questioned how PSDB will impact the job market for accountants, also with multiple answers. About 40% of the responses are that knowledge about PSDB improves the qualification of professionals, and professionals who only “deliver guides” were removed from the market, a response that represents 27% of the data. Another 17% reported that PSDB will increase the workforce to serve companies, given the complexities shown in the previous figure. 7% reveal that PSDB will reduce the workforce to serve their customers, another 7% do not see any influence. Finally, 3% report that it causes a lot of stress and limits the time to resolve other issues. The scenario can be seen in Figure 3:

Figure 3 Project with the greatest impact and Influences in the labor market

Source: The authors

Finally, the professionals were asked what would be most important for them to exercise their role responsibly towards the companies that perform their services. More than one response was collected per professional. Of the respondents, 50% reported that the most important thing for them to carry out their profession responsibly is the proper professional qualification. Another 23% said that the responsibility is linked to the correct interpretation of the legislation together with the understanding of the PSDB manuals, which serve to better fill in the information. Another 23% mention computer skills and managerial vision, and finally 3% mentioned other responses such as patience when carrying out activities.

It was questioned how, in the perception of professionals, PSDB contributes to the improvement of accounting services, also with more than one answer. In this question, the division was very concentrated in three answers, with 41% reporting that PSDB brings faster generation of accounting information. 33% said that it improves the quality of information and 26% say that PSDB connects professionals to the management and controllership area of companies that perform services. These responses are tabulated in Figure 4:

Figure 4 : Most important factor for exercising the profession and PSDB's Contribution to the provision of services:

Source: The authors

Among the questions asked, the operability of PSDB projects and specific questions regarding the operation within the work environment when the professional will transmit the advisory obligations were also questioned. These questions echoed in the general answer that PSDB is complex and requires specific knowledge for its correct operation.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The main purpose of the study was to describe the perceptions of the PSDB implementation and operationalization process by accounting professionals in Irati-PR. Responding to the objectives of the present study, the profession was characterized along with the information technology that is being represented today by all the projects of the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping (PSDB). Analyzing this scenario, the data show that professionals today are relatively young and with a working time of up to 5 years, and men and women are in total equality in the profession.

The impact of PSDB on contemporary accounting was also verified and the data show that the impact is mainly linked to projects that need monthly attention, that is, they are delivered periodically. Invoice projects also represent considerable impacts and finally the annual delivery projects that change the way of showing information in each period.

The questions that reflect the professionals' perception of the most important factors for exercising the profession in a responsible and correct manner, and how PSDB contributes to

the performance of the services, were the ones that most contributed to form the conclusion that professional qualification, together with the interpretation of tax legislation are the main factors for exercising the profession in a responsible manner, and PSDB contributes to speeding up information, improving its quality and linking accounting professionals with managerial and strategic areas within companies.

The perception of professionals regarding the implementation of PSDB is positive, and they are also convinced that constant updating of technical knowledge is necessary in order to responsibly exercise their profession, thus fulfilling their role within companies and society in a responsible manner. general.

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